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The Inhibitory Effect of Bismuth Complexes on SARS Coronavirus

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Although the world is expecting effective and safe COVID-19 vaccines, the search for effective SARS-CoV-2 drug therapies should not be stopped. One of the possible drug candidates for the treatment of COVID-19 are bismuth complexes, but further research is mandatory.

INTRODUCION

Coronaviruses are important human and animal pathogens. At the end of 2019, a novel coronavirus was identified as the cause of a cluster of pneumonia cases in Wuhan, a city in the Hubei Province of China. It rapidly spread, resulting in an epidemic throughout China, followed by an increasing number of cases in other countries throughout the world. In February 2020, the World Health Organization designated the disease COVID-19, which stands for coronavirus disease 2019. The virus that causes COVID-19 is designated severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)¹.

INHIBITORY EFFECT OF BISMUTH COMPLEXES ON SARS CORONAVIRUS

A group of researchers published a study in *Nature Microbiology* in which they tested a set of metallodrugs and related compounds, and identified ranitidine bismuth citrate, a commonly used drug for the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, as a potent anti-SARS-CoV-2 agent, both in vitro and in vivo. Ranitidine bismuth citrate exhibited low cytotoxicity and protected SARS-CoV-2-infected cells with a high selectivity index of 975. Ranitidine bismuth citrate suppressed SARS-CoV-2 replication, leading to decreased viral loads in both upper and lower respiratory

tracts, and relieved virus-associated pneumonia in a golden Syrian hamster model. In vitro studies showed that ranitidine bismuth citrate and its related compounds exhibited inhibition towards both the ATPase ($IC_{50} = 0.69 \mu M$) and DNA-unwinding ($IC_{50} = 0.70 \mu M$) activities of the SARS-CoV-2 helicase via an irreversible displacement of zinc(II) ions from the enzyme by bismuth(III) ions. These findings highlight viral helicase as a druggable target and the clinical potential of bismuth(III) drugs or other metallodrugs for the treatment of SARS-CoV-2 infection².

In another study authors concluded that bismuth complexes including ranitidine bismuth citrate effectively inhibit the nucleoside triphosphate hydrolase and DNA unwinding activities of the SARS coronavirus (SCV) helicase and dramatically reduce SCV replication levels in infected cells. Bismuth nitrilotriacetate, bismuth nitrate, bismuth tricysteine complex, and ranitidine bismuth citrate appeared to be the most efficacious inhibitors of ATPase activity, all showing significant inhibition at a concentration of $1 \mu M$. The similarity in inhibitory potential of these three compounds suggests that the bismuth ion plays the key role in the inhibitory effects. Bismuth ethylenediaminetetraacetate was a surprisingly poor inhibitor, indicating that the complexing groups should not bind to the bismuth (Bi^{3+}) too tightly. These findings suggest that bismuth-based drugs should be further evaluated for the treatment of SCV infections in vivo³.

A study conducted by Shu and coworkers shows that SARS-CoV-2-encoded nonstructural protein 13 (nsp13) possesses the nucleoside triphosphate hydrolase (NTPase) and RNA helicase activities that can hydrolyze all types of NTPs and unwind RNA helices dependently of the presence of

NTP, and further characterize the biochemical characteristics of these two enzymatic activities associated with SARS-CoV-2 nsp13. They also found that bismuth salts could effectively inhibit both the NTPase and RNA helicase activities of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 in a dose-dependent manner. Authors used three different bismuth salts, including bismuth potassium citrate (BPC), ranitidine bismuth citrate (RBC), and bismuth citrate (BC). The data showed that all these bismuth salts inhibited the ATPase activity of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 at 10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, as BPC and RBC showed stronger inhibitory effects than BC. They also found that 10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ BPC or RBC almost abolished the RNA helix unwinding activity of nsp13; on the other hand, although BC treatment also effectively inhibited the RNA helicase activity of nsp13, its inhibitory efficiency was in much less than BPC or RBC. To further characterize the inhibitory effect of BPC or RBC on the NTPase and RNA helicase activities of SARS-CoV-2, researchers treated recombinant nsp13 with increasing concentrations of either bismuth salts. The data show that either BPC or RBC could inhibit the ATPase and helicase activities of MBP-nsp13 in a dose-dependent manner. These findings demonstrate the NTPase and helicase activities of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13, which may play an important role in SARS-CoV-2 replication and serve as a target for antivirals⁴.

There is also one case report that describes a temporal improvement of a COVID-19 positive Chron's disease patient that was treated with a bismuth subsalicylate. The patient was prescribed bismuth subsalicylate (BSS) 525 mg orally 2–4 times a day. Within 6 h of the first dose, his diarrhea was improved. Over the next 6 days, with BSS as his only additional medication, he had steady improvement of his diarrhea, cough, appetite, energy, and well-being; both diarrhea and cough were 80% improved after 6 days of BSS. By day 10, his cough was gone and stooling nearly normal, off BSS. Authors believe that both his diarrhea and cough improved because of BSS⁵.

CONCLUSION

Although the world is expecting effective and safe COVID-19 vaccines, the search for effective SARS-CoV-2 drug therapies should not be stopped, especially when given into account that COVID-19 neutralizing antibodies do not last more than 5-7 months⁶. Moreover, the first generation of COVID-19 vaccines might not reduce the transmission of the virus effectively⁷.

One of the possible drug candidates for the treatment of COVID-19 are bismuth complexes, but further research is mandatory.

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